

SIMULATION OF SAND PRODUCTION PREDICTION IN GAS RESERVOIRSIbrahim Ayuba ^{*1}H. Isma'il ²T.S. Manasseh ³M.S. Gwio ⁴M.M. Aminu ⁵^{*1, 2, 3, 4 & 5}Department of Petroleum Engineering, Bauchi, Nigeria
Ibrahimayuba08@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

Sand production due to result of unconsolidated grains in wellbore formations, as lead to many adverse effect, such as plugging, accumulation in surface equipment, increase in skin and tubing roughness. Sensitivity analysis using PROSPER software was run on different well parameters, (tubing roughness, skin) and under free gas effect for an open hole completion to predict effect of sand production in life of the well. The tubing and skin analysis shows a decline in well flow potential across the years, due to sand production. The future performance indicate sand control remedy must be deploy to maintain and revive the well to it optimum flow potential.

Analysis on free gas effect was used to determine the highest free gas value under the reservoir condition for the well optimum production. (3.5 - 4.023) MMscf/day gave the optimal flow potential for the well. This analysis shows the amount and condition of free gas in the well before the effect of sand production

Keywords: Unconsolidated grains, Sand production, Wellbore formations, Plugging, Accumulation, PROSPER software, Tubing roughness, Open hole completion, Skin analysis, Free gas, Optimal flow potential.

INTRODUCTION

Sand prediction model have the capability to indicate whether initial sand production may take place somewhere during the lifetime of an oil gas field. Prediction of maximum sand-free production rate provides information for sand-control decisions and allows maximization of rate in those wells that are completed without sand control. In this paper, filed data will be used for modelling and making this predictions.

A significant proportion of the world gas reserves is contained in weakly consolidated sandstone reservoirs and hence is prone to sand production. Material degradation is a key process leading to sanding. Drilling operations, cyclic effects of shut-in and start-up, operational conditions, reservoir pressure depletion, and strength-weakening effect of water may gradually lead to sandstone degradation around the perforations and boreholes. High pressure gradient due to fluid flow also facilitates the detachment of sand particles. In addition, fluid flow is responsible for the transport and production of cohesionless sand particles or detached sand clumps to the wellbore. Sand production is the cause of many problems in the oil industry and it affects the completion adversely. These problems include, but are not limited to, plugging the perforations or production liner, wellbore instability, failure of sand control completions

Sand-production problems can be experienced in various ways. In conventional oil wells, transient sand production, where the sand production rate declines rapidly with time, is frequently experienced during the clean-up period after processes such as perforating or acidizing, after rapid bean-up of production, or after water breakthrough. It is assumed that sand production in these cases is merely the removal of weakened or sheared and dilated sand. However, there are different "types" of sand-production behavior. Conventional-oil sand production has been classified on the basis of distinct reservoir evolution stages:

- The early transient sand-production period, when some of the perforation-induced damage has been removed and the cavities may have a zone of reduced permeability around them, leading to a steep exit gradient.
- A stable production period with enlarged cavities, when the damaged zone and the permeability impairment have been removed.
- A general increase in sand influx after a water-cut increase, a process that is considered to be related to capillary forces and is a type of flow-rate-induced sand production.

- An unstable sand-production period because of reservoir pressure depletion, considered to arise when large effective-stress increase causes straining, destroy cohesion, alter fabric, and induce almost-continuous sanding.

Common Techniques Used in Sand Management Decisions

A number of approaches have been developed to predict or help to understand the sand production problem, using physical model testing, analytical and empirical relationships, and numerical models. Routine laboratory tests can only predict the onset of sand production. More sophisticated Physical model could predict volumetric sand production, they are also time-consuming and expensive. In addition, because of the small sizes of the laboratory setup, the results are usually influenced by boundary effects. Analytical models are fast and easy to use but they are only suitable to predict the onset of sand production and they have limitations. Most of them are only valid for capturing a single mechanism of sanding and under simplified geometrical and boundary conditions which are not usually the complicated field-scale problems. Numerical models are by far the most powerful tools for predicting sand production. They can be combined with analytical correlations to obtain the results more efficiently. Experimental results are also utilized to calibrate or validate a numerical model. Yet, numerical models have their own limitations and extensive efforts have been made to improve them.

Discrete element method (DEM) is a useful tool to simulate sand production especially to understand the mechanism of sanding. However, it cannot be used for large scale problems because of large computational time required. (Thallak et al. 1991), have used discrete element models to predict the development of borehole breakouts in an assemblage of spherical particles.

The calibration of the model is also difficult and involves several uncertainties as it is not possible to create a model with the exact particle arrangement as the real material. Further, methodologies to directly measure sandstone micro properties have not been developed yet. Presently, the micro-properties are obtained in calibrating against the actual sand behavior. Therefore, continuum-based models are more popular especially for field-scale problems. However, there can be advanced models which couple continuum and discontinuum models together to take advantage of both methods, these are known as hybrid models.

Modeling of sand production requires coupling of two mechanisms, the first mechanism is mechanical instability and degradation around the wellbore and the second one is hydro-mechanical instability due to low-induced pressure gradient on degraded material surrounding the cavity (e.g perforation and open hole).

At larger perforation lengths, as for openhole production conditions, the effects of non-Darcy flow on rock yielding are not very significant. This conclusion is consistent with the findings of (Wang and Peden, 1991).

In general, numerical methods in the mechanical modeling are categorized under continuum and discontinuum approaches.

In the continuum approach, matters are treated as continuous in deriving the governing differential equations. The assumption of continuity implies that the material cannot be separated or broken into smaller pieces. In the case when there is a discontinuity, the magnitudes of deformation along or across the discontinuity are about the same as the rest of the continuum.

Numerical models based on discontinuum approach sand production is a continuous and dynamic process that occurs at the microscopic scale and the rock becomes a discontinuum in nature, discontinuum approach is promising to simulate phenomena such as detachment of individual particles from the rock matrix.

Other techniques used for predicting sand includes; Formation Strength; Sonic Log; Formation Properties Log; Porosity; Drawdown Finite Element Analysis; Time Dependence.

Formation Strength

Rock failure and/or degradation is commonly accepted as prerequisite for sanding. Failure of geo-materials is usually associated with formation of shear bands which are narrow zones of concentrated plastic deformation. This phenomenon, which is known as “deformation localization” or simply “localization,” is one of the key parameters in sanding prediction models. Further details about this concept can be found in (Sulem et al.1999), (Nouri et al.2009), and (Jafarpour et al.2012).

The general procedure followed by most operators considering whether or not sand control is required, is to determine the hardness of the formation rock (i.e., the rock’s compressive strength). Since the rock’s compressive strength has the same units as the pressure drawdown in the reservoir, the two parameters can be compared on a one to one basis and drawdown limits for specific wells can be determined.

Finite Element Analysis

Probably the most sophisticated approach to predicting sand production is the use of geo-mechanical numerical models developed to analyze fluid flow through the reservoir in relation to the formation strength. The effects of

formation stress associated with fluid flow in the immediate region around the wellbore are simultaneously computed with finite element analysis. While this approach is by far the most rigorous, it requires an accurate knowledge of the formation's strength both in the elastic and plastic regions where the formation begins to fail. The finite element analysis method is good from the viewpoint of comparing one interval with another; however, the absolute values calculated may not represent actual formation behavior.

Drawdown

The pressure drawdown associated with production may be an indicator of potential formation sand production. No sand production may occur with low pressure drawdown around the well whereas excessive drawdown can cause formation material to be produced at unacceptable levels. The amount of pressure drawdown is normally associated with the formation permeability and the viscosity of the produced fluids.

Sonic Log

The sonic log can be used as a way of addressing the sand production potential of wells. The sonic log records the time required for sound waves to travel through the formation in microseconds. The porosity is related to the sonic travel time. Short travel times, (for example, 50 microseconds) are indicative of low porosity and hard, dense rock; while long travel times (for example, 95 microseconds or higher) are associated with softer, lower density, higher porosity rock. A common technique used for determining if sand control is required in a given geologic area is to correlate incidences of sand production with the sonic log readings.

Causes of Sand Production

The solid material produced from a well can consist of both formation fines (usually not considered part of the formation's mechanical framework) and load bearing solids. The production of fines cannot normally be prevented and is actually beneficial.

The following list summarizes many of the factors that influence the tendency of a well to produce Sand, these factors can be categorized into rock strength effects and fluid flow effects

- Degree of consolidation
- Reduction in pore pressure throughout the life of a well
- Production rate
- Reservoir fluid viscosity
- Increasing water production throughout the life of a well
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Degree of Consolidation

The ability to maintain open perforation tunnels is closely tied to how strongly the individual sand grains are bound together. The cementation of a sandstone is typically a secondary geological process and as a general rule, older sediments tend to be more consolidated than newer sediments. This indicates that sand production is normally a problem when producing from shallow, geologically younger Tertiary sedimentary formations. Young Tertiary formations often have little matrix material (cementation material) bonding the sand grains together and these formations are generally referred to as being "poorly consolidated" or "unconsolidated."

Production Rate.

The production of reservoir fluids creates pressure differential and frictional drag forces that can combine to exceed the formation compressive strength. This indicates that there is a critical flow rate for most wells below which pressure differential and frictional drag forces are not great enough to exceed the formation compressive strength and cause sand production.

Reservoir Fluid Viscosity.

The frictional drag force exerted on the formation sand grains is created by the flow of reservoir fluid. This frictional drag force is directly related to the velocity of fluid flow and the viscosity of the reservoir fluid being produced. High reservoir fluid viscosity will apply a greater frictional drag force to the formation sand grains than will a reservoir fluid with a low viscosity.

Modelling

Figure 1: Inflow and Outflow Performance Plot.

The figure above shows the inflow performance relationship curve (IPR) and vertical lift performance (VLP) for an open-hole completion. The well has an absolute open flow 22439.6 (STB/day) with a productivity index of 18.17 when the skin factor is 4 and reservoir pressure of 3242 (psig). Hence this implies deliverability of the well performance is quite effective, (the fluid flow to the reservoir for production). Whereas, the outflow (VLP) is the ability of the reservoir deliver fluid to the tubing to effectively convey to the surface, which will be used to determine and predict the effect of produced sand in this paper work.

Sensitivity Analysis to Predict the Effect of Sand Production

Well Parameters under the effect of Sand Production

<i>Years</i>	Tubing Roughness	Free gas (MMscf/day)	Skin	Liquid rate STB/day	Oil rate STB/day
2016	0.0005	1.5	2	6368.9	4776.4
2017	0.0008	2.78	4	6127.3	4595.5
2018	0.001	4.023	6	5847.2	4385.4
2019	0.005	6.14	8	4956.6	3717.5
2020	0.01	8.55	10	4190.7	3143.0

Initial Condition without Sand

Free gas (MMscf/day)	Liquid (STB/day)	Oil (STB/day)
1.5	6160.8	4580.1
2.78	6222.0	4666.5
4.023	6299.0	4671.7
6.14	6115.9	4586.9
8.55	5894.8	4421.1

From the table above analysis were run on different well parameters under the influence of tubing roughness, skin and the free gas at reservoir condition, for an open-hole production to predict the yearly future performance, without any remedy for sand control.

Due to effect of sand production towards the years the tubing roughness and skin increases, which reduces the flow potential of the well optimum productivity. This is clearly analyzed using the performance plot below.

Figure 2: Performance Plot across the Years.

It can be seen that the production rate declines over year, were a sharp decline was observed in 2018, the use of sand control measure must be used to resolve this sand effect, for the well optimum production.

Condition without Sand

Analysis were run using the differences in free gas at initial well condition were skin and tubing roughness were at fixed parameters without sand production effect, to determine the maximum value of gas that gave the optimum production in the well condition.

Figure 3: Oil Production under Effect of free Gas

The free gas rate from (3.5 - 4.023) MMscf/day gave the highest production rate of 4671.7 (STB/day). This shows the optimal value of free gas rate that will be available in the well for production without sand effect. While the decline in oil production from 4MMscf, is an indication of the frictional pressure loss, were the gas phase travels faster than the liquid phase, therefore leaving behind the oil phase, at this point, more gas will be

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produced to oil, when the amount of gas exceed the production limit. This will help to convey unconsolidated sand grains to surface during production.

Further analysis in PROSPER at a skin of 4 with different tubing roughness are shown below:

CONCLUSION

This paper analysis determines and present a model used to predict sand production, using the petroleum expert software PROSPER, the following features were used to predict sand production, in the flow life of the well.

- The sensitivity analysis on well parameters in predicting the future performance, shows decline in flow potential of the well optimum productivity under the influence tubing roughness and skin, due to the effect of sand production.
- For the free gas effect in the well, analysis indicates (3.5 – 4.023) MMscf/day of free gas in optimizing the well productivity optimally. Above the free gas limit, shows decline in production, due to effect of frictional pressure loss (where the gas phase travels faster than the liquid phase) therefore the well producing more of gas to oil. Hence causing the production of unconsolidated sand grains during cause of production due to high gas rate.

Nomenclature

k	=	Permeability
h	=	Thickness
GOR	=	Gas Oil Ratio
MD	=	Measured Depth
THT	=	Tubing Head Temperature
THP	=	Tubing Head Pressure
IPR	=	Inflow Performance Relationship
VLP	=	Vertical Lift Performance
TVD	=	True Vertical Depth
SSSV	=	Subsurface Safety Valve
PROSPER	=	Production and Systems Performance Analysis Software

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WELL DATA FOR SAND PRODUCTION

PVT Reservoir Data		
Parameter	Quantity	Unit
GOR	700	SCF/STB
Oil gravity	35	API
Gas gravity	0.75	
Water salinity	120000	ppm

PVT Measurement	
Temp	260
Bubble point	3906
Inclination Data	
M.D (Ft)	TVD (Ft)
0	0
7500	7000
10000	9000

Inflow performance Relationship	
RSV pressure	3242.8
RSV temperature	260
Water cut	25
Total GOR	700
k	90
h	110
Drianage area	350
Dietz shape factor	31.6
Skin	4

Production Test Data	
THP	300
THT	180
Water cut	25
Liquid rate	6618
Guage Depth	9850
Guage pressure	2980
RSV pressure	3568.4

Downhole Equipment		
Tubing length	9500	Ft
Tubing LD	3.068	Inches
Casing LD	6.4	Inches
Casing length	10000	Ft
SSSV	2000	Ft
Diameter	2.75	Inches